

MOTIVATIONAL STRATEGIES USED IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING: A META-SYNTHESIS STUDY

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Abstract:

Motivational strategies help students attain the goals to learning language and determine their ultimate success. Since motivation is a personal phenomenon, there are different ways to motivate each student. However, there is scant body of literature on potential usefulness of these strategies to Turkish students learning English language. The purpose of the study is to analyze the existing studies having investigated motivational strategies used in English Language Teaching in Turkey through meta-synthesis method and to reveal the tendency in Turkish literature. Meta-synthesis studies seek to understand and explain a particular phenomenon through the synthesis of individual studies conducted on a particular subject. Synthesis of the studies included into the research reveals potential research topics for the researchers. The findings obtained from the results of the study are explained and discussed in accordance with the research questions. Lastly, potential research areas are suggested for future researches.

Keywords: motivational strategies, english language teaching, meta-synthesis

1. Introduction

Considering that learning actually takes place as a result of the student's really desiring it, it is necessary to include the factors that will increase the students' willingness and

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enthusiasm towards learning in the teaching process. This situation is also valid for language learning. In language teaching, the individual is expected to acquire culture specific properties. There are many factors that shape this process. However, the student's level of motivation in foreign language learning is one of the most important factors determining how successful s/he will be at the end of the process. The high level of motivation will shorten the language learning process and increase its efficiency. Motivation can be defined as the impulse that pushes an individual to achieve an action (Gardner, 1985). Students need to be willing to actively participate in the learning process. While highly motivated students are more willing to take an active role in language learning process, unwilling ones avoid devoting time and making effort in this process. Thus, motivation is one of the major predictors of success in language learning (Dikmen and Ada, 2015, Gardner, 2007). For this reason, language teachers need to provide students with learning conditions that generate motivation in them.

Gardner's (1985) motivation theory is profoundly influential in language learning researches for decades. According to him, motivation consists of three components; that are effort, desire and positive effect. A student's effort and desire to learn target language and extent of joy and pleasure he feels while learning a foreign language determines the level of competence gained. (Gardner, 2001). Also, Gardner emphasizes the role of orientations, or goals which arouse motivation and direct it to reach the goals. If the goal of learning target language is attractive enough in the eyes of student, he will put great effort into learning the targeted language. Two types of orientations, integrative orientation and instrumental orientation, were introduced by Gardner (1985). Integrative motivation refers to the desire to get closer to target community and even to become a member of the community without expecting a tangible award. On the other hand, the instrumental orientation, a counter-part to integrative motivation, refers to desire to learn language for pragmatic reasons, such as getting a higher salary or better job. Expectations of students must be consistent with amount of effort they make to fulfill these expectations. Otherwise, students may experience a lack of motivation. Resultantly, both integrative and instrumental motivation is needed to maintain the motivation pushing students to make effort to learn a language (Dede and Argün, 2004). As the person managing teaching and learning process, teacher is responsible of presenting students an optimal learning environment that promotes motivation to accomplish attained goals in language learning.

L2 motivational self-system is another motivational model proposed by Dörnyei (2005). The model consists of three concepts that are ideal L2 self, ought-to L2 self, and L2 learning experience. Ideal L2-self represents the ideal image of an individual in return for learning a second language and it relates to the future advantages of learning a second language. A student's expectations for his future self-identity determine the extent of his motivation in language learning. For example, a student's desire to create oneself as a native-like speaker might act as a powerful motivator in language learning process. The student, desiring to reduce the discrepancy between actual and ideal self, native-like speaker, will make an effort to reach the desired goal. Contrary to ideal-self,

ought to L2-self is concerned with the negative outcomes a student wants to avoid or expectations he wants to fulfill in return of learning language. Perceived obligations, duties and responsibilities are related to the ought-to-L2 self. A student desiring to please her family, or having a fear of failing the class develops ought-to-self motivation in language learning process. Lastly, L2 learning experience relates to existing learning situation. The students enjoying the learning environment takes a positive attitude to learning language. It is obvious that foreign language teachers are responsible of taking necessary measures to help students gain awareness about advantages of learning a foreign language in order to increase their willingness to learn language.

Teachers are leaders of the teaching and learning process and they have a profound influence on the improvement of students' motivation. Proper teacher behaviors are among the motivational factors for most of the students. Therefore, the motivational strategies used by teachers in foreign language teaching might facilitate the learning process and affect the motivation level of the students. Guilloteaux and Dörnyei (2008) define motivational strategies as the instructional interventions teachers use to elicit and stimulate student motivation. According to them, motivational strategies are categorized into four dimensions. First, teachers need to establish a good rapport with their students, support classroom cohesion with proper group norms, and create a supportive and pleasant classroom atmosphere in order to create basic motivational conditions. The strategies in the second dimension aim at generating initial student motivation and they entail strategies designed to increase students' expectancy of success and develop positive attitudes towards language learning. Thirdly, teachers need to promote situation-specific task motivation, provide learners with experience of success, allow students to maintain a positive social image, and promote learner autonomy in order to maintain and protect motivation. Effective and encouraging feedback, increasing student satisfaction, offering grades in a motivational manner, and adaptive attributions are the strategies in the last dimension that is encouraging positive retrospective self-evaluation.

Motivational strategies help students attain the goals as to learning language and determine their ultimate success. Since motivation is a personal phenomenon, there are different ways to motivate each student (Dörnyei, 2005). These strategies demonstrate a systematic way for both teachers and the students in teaching-learning process. However, there is scant body of literature on potential usefulness of these strategies to Turkish students learning English language. The absence of an extensive study illustrating the motivational strategies used in English language teaching in Turkey is the main reason behind the current study. Obviously, the influence of motivational strategies might differ depending on the age, gender, socio-economic level, language level, or class grades of the students. Similarly, effective strategies might differ in view of students and teachers. Taken together, there seems to be a need for the researches investigating the relationship between the motivational strategies and such variables. Consequently, it is necessary to establish a theoretical framework for the researchers to investigate motivational strategies in English language learning and to discover the

deficiencies in the body of literature on this subject in order to shed a light on potential future researches.

2. Research Method

Meta-synthesis method was adopted in the study. Meta-synthesis studies seek to understand and explain a particular phenomenon through the synthesis of individual studies conducted on a particular subject. A number of different but interrelated studies are compared and contrasted so as to develop an explanatory theory or model which could explain the findings on the phenomenon and provide researchers with a theoretical framework. Synthesis of the studies included into the research reveals potential research topics for the researchers. Therefore, it is recommended to limit the number of studies included into meta-synthesis studies (Çalık and Sözübilir, 2014, Walsh and Downe, 2005). Meta-synthesis aims to combine the results of interrelated studies with different content. The data source of the meta-synthesis study is generated from the studies that are previously carried out and the sample is formed in accordance with the relevancy of the topics (Bondas and Hall, 2007). In the analysis process, studies on a specific subject are analyzed according to predetermined themes and sub-themes, and the results of the study are interpreted by associating them with research questions and grounding on appropriate qualitative and quantitative data (Walsh and Downe, 2005; Erwin et al, 2011). Meta-synthesis studies provide participants with a multi-faceted and detailed view of the research as they involve the participants, research process and ideas (Lachal et al, 2017).

Seven steps are followed in meta-synthesis studies (Polat and Osman 2015, Aspfors and Fransson 2015). These steps are;

1. Formulating research problem and research questions,
2. Conducting a comprehensive search of the literature
3. Conducting careful appraisal of research studies for possible inclusion.
4. Selecting and conducting meta-synthesis techniques to analyze research studies included into the study.
5. Presenting synthesis of findings across studies
6. Recommendations for future researches on the subject

2.1 Comprehensive Search of the Literature

In the study, after the research questions were formulated, a list of studies that might be included into the meta-synthesis were developed through literature review and document review methods. In this step, theses that were conducted through the years 2000-2018 and on the subject “motivational strategies in English Language Teaching” were searched in research engine of Turkey’s national thesis center. Also, the Turkish journals were reviewed in order to access the articles published on the subject within the years 2000-2018. While searching the articles and theses, the key words identified were as follows: “*motivation, motivation level, language education, foreign language teaching, demotivation, motivational teacher characteristics, effective teacher, effective teacher*”

characteristics, etc.”. Ultimately, 20 Master’s theses and 3 articles published in national journals in Turkey were accessed and saved in an electronic folder.

2.2 Appraisal of Research Studies for Possible Inclusion

In the second step, proper studies to be synthesized were appraised based on the exclusion and inclusion criteria. For this aim, among the studies saved in the folder, the ones meeting the following selection criteria were included into the study.

- Was the study carried out with teachers working at different school levels/grades in Turkey or teacher candidates studying English language teaching at one of the universities in Turkey, or students receiving education at schools or universities in Turkey?
- Was the study carried out by Turkish researchers?
- Did the study investigate motivational strategies in English language learning or teaching?
- Were the research questions, method, design, participants, sample group, data collection instruments, and findings articulated clearly in the study?

After the studies that did not comply with the stated criteria were eliminated, final sample of studies entailed 2 articles published in Turkish journals and 9 MA theses with PDF extension from National Thesis Center of Council of Higher Education Board. As none of the existing PhD dissertations covered the subject “motivational strategies in English language learning or teaching”, PhD dissertations fell outside the scope of the study. At the end of this step, final sample of studies to be synthesized were determined and the scope of the study was limited to 11 scientific researches (Sarıyer, 2008; Vural, 2007; Görgeç et al, 2009; Atay, 2004; Keleş, 2007; Özsöz, 2007; Taşpınar, 2004; Aslantürk, 2009; Kahraman, 2014; Öztürk, 2012; Yurtsever, 2017).

One of the researches (Yurtsever, 2017) were examined within the scope of the study although its title didn’t contain the expression “motivational strategies”. As the study investigated the effect of motivational activities proposed by Dörnyei and Ushioda (2013), the researchers reached a consensus on including the study into the meta-synthesis.

2.3 Coding the Data

In data coding stage, the studies within the scope of the meta-synthesis were read through more than once by two researchers. After, key concepts were determined in accordance with the research questions asked and in a Microsoft excel file, all the studies were coded according to the key concepts by two researchers. The studies were named “A1, A2, A3....A11” in the excel file.

2.4 Validity and Reliability of the Study

In order to ensure the validity and reliability, the studies to be included into the meta-synthesis were determined by two researchers cooperatively and the studies selected were submitted for the approval of an expert in curriculum and instruction. While coding the data, the studies were read through by two researchers more than once and

coded in the excel file cooperatively. An expert opinion was sought in case of any conflict arising between the researchers throughout the entire research process. Last, the research process and the results obtained were presented clearly.

2.5 Data Analysis

Content analysis method was used to analyze the data. The data was analyzed in accordance with predetermined themes and subthemes parallel to the research questions and the results were presented in the tables or graphs with a frequency value.

3. Results

The findings obtained from the results of the study are explained in accordance with the research questions. The results that relate to the first research question “Which purposes and research questions did the existing studies have?” are given in the Table 1.

Table 1: Purposes and research questions of the existing studies

Purpose	Study	Frequency
Finding out motivational strategies used while delivering instruction	A1, A2, A3, A4, A6, A9, A10	7
Finding out the effective strategies according to teachers and students	A2, A5, A8, A9, A10, A11	6
Finding out motivational teacher behaviors	A2, A9, A10, A11	5
Finding out the frequency of motivational strategies	A1, A2, A6, A7	4
Finding out the relationship between student motivation and motivational strategies	A8, A9	2
Finding out the significant motivational strategies in view of teacher candidates	A3	1
Finding out the relationship between motivational strategies and teacher characteristics	A6	1
Finding out factors that influence the use of motivational strategies	A7	1
Finding out the motivation type students have	A9	1
Finding out the effect of motivational strategies on student success	A9	1
Finding out the factors that negatively affect motivation	A1	1

As illustrated in the Table 1, while 7 of the 11 studies carried out between the years 2000-2018 in Turkey aimed to find out the motivational strategies teachers use while delivering the instruction, 6 studies attempted to identify effective motivational strategies in view of teachers and students. Similarly, 4 out of 7 studies searched for the frequency of various motivational strategies used by teachers and 5 studies investigated teacher behaviors motivating students to learn English language. Last, discovering the relationship between the motivation of students and motivational strategies was the purpose of two studies. Lastly, single studies were designed to determine significant motivational strategies in view of teacher candidates, factors that affect student motivation negatively, the relationship between motivational strategies and teacher

characteristics, factors determining the use of motivational strategies, motivation type students have, and effect of motivational strategies on students' success.

The answer to the second research question "Which subject areas were dealt with in the existing studies?" was received from the experimental study coded A9. As the rest of the studies were not in experimental design, any subject areas were not covered in these studies. The subject areas dealt with in the study, A9, were greetings, portraits, my future L2 self, reality check, overcoming obstacles, study plan, task map, work style, study contracts, rate yourself, goods and services: in a restaurant, social: at a party, work: job interview, festivals, where can I get a cup of coffee?

The third research question of the study is 'which research methods and designs were used in the existing studies?' Concerning the third research question, the results are presented in the Table 2.

Table 2: Research methods and designs used in the existing studies

Method		Study	F
Quantitative	Survey	A1, A3, A4, A8,	4
	Experimental	A9	1
Qualitative		A6	1
Mixed		A2, A5, A7, A10, A11	5

As shown in the Table-2, the existing studies on motivational strategies used in English Language Teaching adopted either qualitative or quantitative methods. Only study having followed qualitative method was the one coded A6. Also, it is seen that none of the existing studies was designed as an experimental study except the one coded A9. Concerning the fourth research question "Which groups of participants and sample groups were included into the existing studies?", the results are presented in the Table 3.

Table 3: Groups of participants and sample groups included into the existing studies

	Participants		School Type			Level of Education			
	Teacher	Student	Teacher Candidate	State	Private	Primary	High School	University Preparatory	Under-graduate
A1	*	*		*			*		
A2	*	*		*				*	
A3			*	*					*
A4	*			*	*	*			
A5	*			*				*	
A6	*			*				*	
A7	*			*		*			
A8	*	*		*				*	
A9		*		*			*		
A10		*		*	*			*	
A11	*	*		*				*	

As demonstrated in the Table 3, teachers, students and teacher candidates constituted of participants of the studies carried out within the years 2000-2018 about the motivational strategies used in English language teaching. While 4 out of 11 existing studies were conducted with teachers, 2 studies were undertaken with students, and the number of studies carried out with both teachers and students is 4. Last, A3-coded study is unique in terms that it is the only study that examined the motivational strategies in view of teacher candidates.

Regarding the school types, it is seen that all of the researches were carried out in public schools or universities. The studies coded A4 and A10 were carried out both at public and private schools and public and private universities, respectively.

Finally, classification of the studies according to the education levels indicate that a great number of existing studies were done at university level. While 6 studies, A2, A5, A6, A8, A10, A11, were done at preparatory programs, A3-coded study was carried out at an undergraduate program, English language teaching program, at university level. Last, it is seen that there are 2 studies carried out either at primary (A4, A7) or at high school (A1, A9) level. A9-coded study was carried out at a vocational high school.

Concerning the fifth research question “which data collection instruments were used in the existing studies?”, the results are shown in Graph-1.

Graph 1: Data collection instruments used in the existing studies

As seen in the Graph-1, the data was collected through questionnaires or scales in almost all the existing studies on motivational strategies in English language teaching (A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A7, A8, A9, A10, A11). The A6-coded study is unique in terms that neither a questionnaire nor a scale was used as a data collection instrument in the study. Besides, the studies in which interview form or questions were used as an instrument are the ones coded A2, A5, A6, A7, A9, A10, and A11 and observation forms were used in the studies coded A2, A6, A7, and A9. Finally, the only study in which achievement test was used as a data collection instrument is the study coded A9.

Regarding the last question, “What kind of findings were reported in the existing studies?”, the results were as follows:

Table 4: Findings reported in the existing studies

Findings	Studies	f
According to the students, positive teacher and student relationship is the most effective motivational strategy supporting their learning English	A1,A2, A10,A11,A7	5
According to the students, activities that breaks the monotony of the lessons and make them interesting and fun improve motivation of the students.	A1,A12, A10,A11, A7	5
Teachers mostly use the motivational strategies creating a positive atmosphere in the classroom by being tolerant of mistakes, using positive reinforcement, being energetic and good-humored.	A1,A2,A4, A5,A7,A8	6
Teachers mostly use and give importance to such task-related motivational strategies as bringing fun activities to the class, caring the interests and needs of students while preparing activities, choosing challenging activities.	A1,A2,A4, A5,A7,A8, A6	7
Self-confidence-building strategies such as expressing students' belief in what they can do and encouraging students to do better are among the strategies that the teachers use most.	A1,A5,A7, A8	4
Strategies for introducing target culture are among the least frequently used strategies by teachers.	A1, A2,A7	3
According to students, motivational strategies used for creating positive classroom atmosphere improve their motivation.	A1,A2, A10, A11	4
Authentic materials is rarely used by teachers while delivering instruction.	A2,A6	2
Teachers rarely use the strategies supporting student autonomy.	A1,A7	2
Teachers use motivational strategies independently from student interests and needs; therefore, they should pay more attention to the interests and needs of students while preparing lessons.	A8,A9	2
According to the students, teachers' effort to introduce target culture increases motivation.	A1	1
Motivational strategies teachers use and care differ depending on gender.	A3	1
Motivational strategies teachers use and care do not differ depending on gender.	A7	1
Teachers in private schools use motivational strategies more frequently than teachers at state schools.	A4	1
Teachers are not responsible for motivating students because of their age range.	A6	1
Teaching style of teachers, the activities used in the classroom, personality traits of students, curriculum-related problems and school-related problems may yield demotivation in view of students.	A1	1
The socio-economic structure of the school districts influence type and frequency of motivational strategies teachers use at lessons.	A7	1
In-class activities prepared in accordance with motivational strategies are effective on increasing student motivation.	A9	1

As illustrated in the Table 4, the findings of the existing studies on motivational strategies in English language teaching are mainly related to strategies teachers or students find effective. Initially, the findings reported in the studies coded A1, A2, A10, A11, A7 revealed that motivational strategies that aim at developing positive teacher-student rapport are the most effective strategies in view of students. Secondly, the findings of the studies coded A1, A12, A10, A11, A7 proved that the activities that make lessons more interesting and enjoyable by breaking the routine positively affect student motivation. Similarly, according to the findings of the studies coded A1, A2, A10, A11, strategies used to create a positive classroom environment improve student motivation.

Regarding the effective strategies in view of teachers, findings confirm that creating positive classroom environment, presenting tasks effectively, increasing self-confidence of students are the motivational strategies teachers mostly use and care. Last, bringing authentic materials to the classroom, making effort to support learner autonomy are rarely used by teachers to motivate students.

In addition to similar findings reported in the studies, the contradictory findings were obtained, as well. For instance, while gender differences was found to be a determinant of motivational strategies teachers use according to the findings of A3-coded study, contradictory findings were reported in the study coded A7. Also, effective strategies differ in view of teachers and students according to the findings of the existing studies. Although introduction of target culture was found to be an effective strategy in view of students in the 3 studies coded A1, A2, A7, it was reported among the least frequently used strategies in the study coded A1. Likewise, the findings reported in the studies coded A8 and A9 confirms these contradictory results. The findings of these studies indicated that teachers use motivational strategies independently of students' interests and needs. Last, the only experimental study, A9, proved that motivation-oriented activities play a productive role in increasing student motivation.

Finally, the results obtained from single studies are as follows: teachers at private schools use motivational strategies more frequently than teachers at public schools (A4), teachers disbelieve they are responsible of motivating students because of their age range (A6), teaching style of teachers, the activities used in the classroom, personality traits of students, curriculum-related problems and school-related problems may cause demotivation among students (A1), and the socio-economic structure of the school districts have an influence on type and frequency of motivational strategies used by teachers (A7).

4. Discussion

The findings emerging from the meta-synthesis of the studies carried out between the years 2000-2018 in Turkey about motivational strategies in English language teaching will be discussed in relation to the research questions. On the other hand, before discussing the findings, it is worth mentioning that there is a scant body of literature on the subject; therefore, motivational strategies seem to be a research area in need of further studies. As the studies investigating the motivational strategies within the pre-determined time period were few in number, only 11 studies could be examined within the scope of the study. While the earliest study was conducted by Atay and Taşpınar (2004), the most recent one was conducted by Yurtsever (2017). For this reason, it is obvious that effectiveness of motivational strategies still need to be explored and confirmed by further studies. Also, body of knowledge on the subject should be increased in quality and quantity.

First of all, regarding the purposes of the existing studies, most of them attempted to identify effective motivational strategies in view of students and teachers.

While only 2 studies investigated the relationship between the motivational strategies used by the teachers and the ones students find effective, a single study investigated effective strategies depending on different teacher characteristics. In a similar way, the effect of motivation-oriented activities on student success was searched in only one study. The findings indicate that studies on motivational strategies in English language teaching need to vary in purpose. In order to achieve more meaningful and accurate results, there seems to be a need for higher number of studies investigating the effect of motivational strategies on student achievement and studies investigating the relationship between the strategies teachers use and the student motivation.

In addition, motivation of the students is not constant and fluctuates throughout the lesson or academic year (Busse and Walter, 2008, Lamb, 2007). The studies finding out the proper motivational strategies to generate and maintain high motivation either at different parts of academic year or different parts of lesson might be recommended as a potential research topic for the researchers.

Concerning the second research question, motivational strategies in relation to different subject areas have been examined in a single study so far. For this reason, it is necessary to examine motivational strategies in relation to different subject areas.

Concerning the third research question, a great number of existing studies were designed either as survey studies, one of quantitative methods, or mix-method studies. Only one experimental study on the subject was done between the years 2000-2018. Likewise, a single study used qualitative method to examine motivational strategies. The findings show that it is necessary to conduct studies with different research methods and designs. Instead of surveys that offer a descriptive edge on the subject studied, longitudinal studies will be beneficial to examining the relationship between the strategies used by teachers and student motivation. By this way, more comprehensive and in-depth information on the subject will be obtained (Karasar, 1995). In addition, action research studies are appropriate to seek solutions for demotivation problems students in language classes have. Apart from this, single-case studies might be designed to report the change in motivation of individual students in reaction to different motivational strategies teachers use (Creswell, 2014).

Related to the fourth research question, the participants and sample groups of the existing studies were examined. The studies on the subject were conducted mostly with students learning English in preparatory programs at universities. 2 out of 11 studies were carried out at primary and 2 studies at high schools, and both studies conducted at primary schools were carried out with teachers. In other words, there is a need for studies investigating effective motivational strategies in view of students at primary schools. In the same vein, the studies having attempted to diagnose effective strategies in view of teachers or students at high schools are few in number. While one of the two studies was done at an Anatolian high school, the second one was carried out at a vocational high school. Therefore, obviously, it is necessary to carry out studies exploring effective motivational strategies depending on diverse high school types. Similarly, there are few studies that examined how motivational strategies used in public or private schools differ in view of teachers and students. As the facilities,

opportunities, and student and teacher characteristics of these two types of schools are different from each other, effective motivational strategies teachers need to use in these schools will differ, too, which is among potential research areas for future researches. The only study having compared the frequency of motivational strategies used by teachers at public and private schools were done by Atay (2004). Thus, the studies comparing and contrasting motivational strategies used at public and private schools should be increased in number. Also, there is a need for the future studies exploring effective strategies for each type of school in depth. Finally, as mentioned above, only study investigating effective strategies in view of teacher candidates was carried out by Görden et al. (2009), so a greater number of studies are needed for confirming the results of this single study and the number of studies done with teacher candidates should be increased, too. In conclusion, it is necessary to examine how effective motivational strategies differ according to different types of schools, educational levels and socio-economic conditions of the school community, and, students and teachers at different types of schools.

Concerning the fifth research question, questionnaires or scales are the most common data collection instruments used in the studies on motivational strategies in English language teaching. In addition, the interview form or observation form are other two data collection instruments used in the existing studies. Unlike the others, achievement test was used in a single study. As most of the existing studies adopted a survey design, questionnaires or scales were the primary data collection instrument used in the studies, and observations and interviews were used to ensure data triangulation in these studies. The only study in which achievement test was used was carried out by Yurtsever (2017). The pre-test post-test design of the study allowed the researcher to use an achievement test. Resultantly, the studies on motivational strategies in English language teaching should vary in design and data collection instruments. In case different research designs were adopted, the data collection instruments would vary, too.

Related to the last research question, it seems there is a mismatch between the motivational strategies teachers and students find effective, they are alike in some ways, though. In students' view, the most effective motivational strategies are the ones aiming at developing teacher-student rapport, breaking the classroom routine, and creating a positive classroom environment, respectively. Contrary to students' preferences, teachers attach most importance to the strategies aiming at creating a positive classroom environment, presenting activities effectively, and increasing students' self-confidence. The results of these studies are in line with a number of studies having attempted to describe ideal teacher behaviors. Teachers' ability to establish positive relationships with students, create a safe classroom environment and to develop supportive attitudes towards students are among the most effective factors that increase student motivation (Özdoğdu, 2015; Canıdar, 2010 and Üstün, 2017). Supportive teacher behaviors are one of the major factors in the improvement of student motivation (Dörnyei, 2001). It is clear that the results of the meta-synthesis study support the results of the existing studies in body of literature.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The results of the study are important in terms of identifying effective motivational strategies that will enable the language learning process to be more efficient by actively involving students into the language learning process. The results of the study might be benefited in order to increase the awareness of teachers about motivational strategies that strengthen student motivation in language learning process. In addition, the results might be beneficial in providing language teachers with in-service trainings on effective motivational strategies. Also, awareness about motivational strategies will help teachers sharpen the skills necessary to prepare effective lessons. Finally, the results of the study are significant in terms of drawing a theoretical framework on the place of motivational strategies in foreign language teaching and presenting new research areas for researchers.

Based on the findings, the recommendations for future studies are as follows:

- There is a need for the studies putting greater emphasis on motivational strategies in English language teaching in order to increase body of knowledge on the subject.
- There is a need for further studies with various purposes as the existing studies are limited in terms of the purposes they have.
- In order to reach more accurate and meaningful results, the studies investigating effective strategies in relation to student achievement should be increased in number, In the same vein, further studies should be designed to examine the changes in student motivation in reaction to the motivational strategies teachers use. As the motivation level of the students fluctuate both throughout a lesson and an academic year, researchers might design studies that aim to identify motivational strategies proper to use at different parts of a lesson, or different times of an academic year in order to maximize students' participation in lessons.
- Different subject areas are addressed only in a study, so motivational strategies that might be used in different subject areas should be found out.
- Regarding the research design of the studies, most of the existing studies were conducted in mixed method, so the future studies adopting qualitative or quantitative method are needed. In addition, longitudinal studies should be designed to examine the relationship between the strategies used by teachers and motivation of students. In addition, action research studies might be designed to examine the effect of motivational strategies used to resolve demotivation problems in language classes. Apart from this, single-case studies examining the change in motivation level of individual students in reaction to different strategies is another potential research area. Last, studies in various designs would let researchers use various data collection instruments.

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